

Wrapped Universes

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the 8-theory and manipulating the second term, of the acceleration, it is possible to derive a new insight about the direction of cosmos expansion. In addition, we can reason why the universe is expanding in time invariant rate by using the Manipulation. Reader is assumed to be familiar with the 8-Theory thesis.

Introduction

The main equation:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial \partial g'}{\partial \partial t} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Given no other data is attainable from the first three terms, we require:

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad -\frac{\partial \partial g'}{\partial \partial t} = 0 \quad (2)$$

In agreement with our model of the universe. Negative time invariant acceleration from areas of extremum curvatures on the manifold.

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial \partial g'}{\partial \partial t} \quad (3)$$

Validating the Einstein equivalence principle between gravity and acceleration.

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial \partial g'}{\partial \partial t} \quad (4)$$

Again, we assume no data is available from the first three terms, no indication they agree with a stationary Lorentz manifold. Now we can represent the equation (1) in a different way, if there are many stationary Lorentz manifolds we can write:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s_1} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s_2} = 0 \quad (5)$$

Alternatively:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial L}{\partial s(n)} = 0 \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial L}{\partial s(n)} \frac{\partial s(n)}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (7)$$

However, they exert pressure or interact at areas of maximal curving, causing each Matrix to accelerate while keeping the points of extremum curvature as they are. The Universe does not expand into anything, it is expanding due to distinct manifolds interaction all required being stationary. Since the acceleration is invariant and affects all the foreseeable part of the universe, we can state the distinct manifold is wrapped or glued to our manifold. Similar to a wave packet, we can form a universe packet. Endless succession of manifolds wrapping our universe and interacting with areas of extremum curvature on our universe, causing an outward acceleration of the matrix.

So the universe does not expand into anything, it expands due to everything according to this representation. However, "everything" that is distinct. Those universes could be more massive, at a different stage of their development and so the moment of singularity in this Universe by no means special. There are infinite distinct singularities. There is not just one universe at a very close distance, there are infinitely many.

References

O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)